

Towards an Automatic Linguistic Quality Assurance of Localized Software and Website based on Multidimensional Quality Metrics

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ABSTRACT

Context: Nowadays, the main attempt of engineers and scholars is to automate the whole or some phases of a process, particularly in the field of software design and development. Testing localized software is also a good area for automation. While there are studies on the topic, however, the available literature does not propose an automation tool on the basis of the well-known error topologies of available quality control models, namely, LISA QA Mode, SAE J2450 and Multidimensional Quality Metrics (MQM). Objectives: In this research, the objective is to propose an approach or tool which can be used during software testing, particularly after localization process to get insight into the linguistic quality state of a localized software or a website. Methods: To this end, seemingly, machine learning algorithms, such as Decision Trees Random Forests, Support Vector Machines (SVM), Neural Networks (e.g., Convolutional Neural Networks, Recurrent Neural Networks) and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) can be employed. Results: After careful consideration of the available literature, and research articles indexed in WoS, Scopus, Science Direct, IEEE Xplore and ACM Digital Library, it was found that there is no systematic approach or a tool for automatic assessment of localized software based on MQM metrics. Conclusion: In conclusion, we need a tool which is capable of automatic quality assurance of localized software, but it is highly critical to develop this tool based on de facto quality standards of software localization industry.

Keywords: Linguistic Quality Assurance, MQM Metrics, Software Localization, Automatic Testing

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, the main concentration of the industrial sectors is to produce and develop products of high quality, which not only meets the needs of the users, but also the products should be in accordance with local conventions of the target market, and software and digital products do need special attention regarding these concerns. Quality can be defined based on five complementary approaches, namely, transcendent approach, product-based approach, user-based approach, manufacturing-based approach and value-based approach [1]. Quality in software: In the field of software, considering the definition of IEEE, quality refers to an extent to which a software product satisfies both functional and non-functional requirements. So, quality is limited or to be more precise confined by the degree to which the realized requirements accurately symbolize the needs and expectations of stakeholders. While software quality assurance encompasses the sequence of activities used for defining and assessing the sufficiency of a software process yield evidence that established confidence that the software process is appropriate for and leads to a software products with decent quality for the intended process [2]. Translation and software localization: For centuries, people have frequently considered translation as applying only to written texts and the majority of the devised theories have always emphasized the notion of "carrying meaning across." Starting from the 1980s, there has been an emergence of other activities plus to with text translation, which have complicated the traditional understanding, such as adapting software for a locale—a variation of a language combined with cultural conventions found in a particular region and such process is generally known as software localization. During software localization, a language service provider (LSP) frequently combines text with other culture- or region-specific content, like graphics, music, currencies, or functional elements, e.g. forms for entering addresses and telephone numbers.

It is evident that localization needs bicultural knowledge and an understanding of the semantics of the items. Figure 1 presents a schematic representation for a broad definition for translation, where localization is included as additional activity in translation.

Fig. 1. A schematic representation of broad definition of translation, including localization.

Dunn [3] points out that localization process is consisted of translation of textual content into the language and textual conventions of the target locale, adaptation of non-textual content (from colors, icons and bitmaps, to packaging, form factors, etc.) and output and delivery mechanisms to take into account the cultural, technical and regulatory requirements of that locale.

Quality in Translation: Among the afore-mentioned approaches for quality definition, the user-based approach is highly relevant to the translation industry, as quality translation should meet the end-users' needs, while this approach is followed by a production-based approach, which put an emphasize on the procedure and the process which are performed to manufacture a product. That is, the producers should adopt and implement a set of practices to increase the chance of producing a good product or service, which has a desirable confirmation with the specifications. This definition of quality is in accordance with the European standard (En 15038)[4]. Normally, it is common to come up with two definitions of translation quality: broad and narrow definitions. The broad definition of translation quality includes the quality basis for many activities as "translation", like summary translation, transcreation, and localization. According to the broad definition of translation quality, a quality translation realizes accuracy and fluency needed by the audience and purpose and complies with all other specifications which are speculated by the requester and provider. While the latter definition of translation quality considers translation a text-centric activity, it ignores a certain aspect of localization. Therefore, it is the choice between the definition of translation quality which guides the practitioners to develop or choose translation quality metrics, which have implications for measuring the quality in the field of all activities under the umbrella of translation [5].

Localized software quality assurance: the quality of localized software products is evaluated by performing "quality assurance" or "testing". In the literature, as in practice, the terms "quality assurance" and "testing" tend to be used interchangeably to refer to the process of inspection, detection, and correction of defects in the target version of the software with respect to the source version. In the interest of clarity, we will refer to this process as "localization testing." Localization testing verify the localized software considering three categories of quality features, namely, linguistic, cosmetic and functional [3]. During linguistic testing, the main concern is accurate translation of the translatable text on the graphical user interface, while cosmetic testing endeavor to guarantee that all text and graphics are aligned correctly and completely in the target

version of the software. Finally, the functional testing focuses on the issues that may be resulted leading break anything or imposing any functional problems into the software due to the localization process.

2. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Nowadays, most software vendors endeavor to export their products to other countries. This mostly originated from the fact that all software companies are determined to be capable of competing in the world market. It is deemed that in the information technology realm, there exists a series of products that are multilingual, such as mail services, airlines information system, car rental websites and so on. Any company that aims at increasing its business should pay heed to the localization industry. These companies aim at delivering a paragon of their product. But different locales and regions of the world recall different cultures, languages and folklores that companies should consider these differences and try to localize their products in a way that it satisfies the clients and end-user expectations. So, it is the turn of the translators and localization engineers to fabricate a high quality translation and deliver a functional localized software, which is also pointed out by [6] who emphasizes that the final objective of the localization process is to fabricate a successful product which is localized per cultural and linguistic conventions, which can lead to increase in the sale of that digital product in the target market.

To this end, there are three QA models that are devised by companies which are active in the sphere of localization. These are LISA QA Model, SAE j2450 and Multidimensional Quality Metrics (MQM). To date, these QA models are developed via collaboration between software engineers, translators and social experts. For Kinds [7], Translation quality is difficult to judge, let alone quantify and the question of how to measure it has long been subject to debate (p.147). Most of the issues that are linked to the translation quality are about the quality of the target text that may not satisfy the client, so "to determine whether someone has attained translation quality, one must be able to measure it [5]. This is also the case in the localization industry and quality of the localized software and QA models are manifold. The quality measurement of a localized product is performed via testing procedures [8]. Testing localized software is an integral part of the whole localization process [9]. Generally, there are different tools of testing which are associated to the software development cycle that a software product should go through several testing cycle before it can be successfully localized and released, these levels are as follows:

- Internationalization testing
- Localization testing
- Functionality testing

In this study, we plan to move toward an automatic linguistic quality assurance of localized software, and as an starting point we have selected two case studies: Banking software and educational consultancy website, www.studyinturkey.net, which provide services for foreign students interested in studying in Turkey. The strings of user interfaces of these products are translated using Google Machine Translation, without any post-editing. It is worth noting that the banking software is original developed for Iranian users, while educational consultancy website is developed for both Iranian and English-speaking users. Hence, we have three language pairs: (Persian, English), (Turkish, Persian) and (Turkish, English). Of course, there is literature on automatic quality assurance of localized software, but none of them are based on specific quality assurance model or metrics. As a result, the present study will be the pioneer which endeavors to propose an automatic approach for linguistic quality assurance of localized software and websites based on MQM.

3. SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

The present research is of high importance mainly due to its main objective which is to make the linguistic quality assurance of a localized software automatic based on MQM framework. Certainly, the present research will yield important implications for academicians of both the software engineering and translation studies department, as well as implications for real-world problems in the localization industry. The implications can be in two aspects: theoretical and practical. The former one refers to the revision in curriculum of translations studies, which can lead to a more emphasis on the linguistic quality aspect of a localized software and providing undergraduate and graduate studies with more workshops and practical courses on quality assurance approaches of software localization, both automatic and manual ones. The latter aspect refers to a movement among the language service providers, as well as software vendors to not only localize software and

applications, but also adopt a proper and scientifically validated automatic method for linguistic quality assurance of a localized software. Indeed, we can encourage them to use automatic quality assurance methods which are based on a established localization quality assessment models, such as MQM.

4. RELATED STUDIES ON QUALITY IN SOFTWARE LOCALIZATION

5.

A comparison between the related studies which have focused on quality assurance of software is tabulated in table 1. Then, the proposal of the present study for automatic linguistic testing of localized software and website is presented.

Table 1. A comparison between the preceding studies on quality assurance in software localization.

Study	Metrics if applied	Quality assessment model if applied or created	Assessment Scope (Textual, layout, etc)	Common features (metrics) with LISA QA Model, SAE j2450 and MQM
[10]	Not available	Not available	Textural, layout, including size, location and alignment of GUI elements	Not available
[11]	Localized resources testing Fallback language Localized media and default resources Ovetranslation Linguistic testing Cosmetic testing Views Swipling Direction Direction-sensitive graphics Auto layout in Views Overlapping Elements' positions Misalignment Text direction String truncation validation Functional Testing	1) Identifying BiDi localization Testing Requirements 2) Identify the issues specific for the requirements 3) Create an effective localization test method specific to each issue Test cases are generated for automatic testing:	Functionality, cosmetically, linguistically and culturally BiDi-languages issues	With Lisa: Language, general style, country With SAE: Syntactic Omission Miscellaneous With MQM: Accuracy Linguistic conventions Style Locale conventions Audience appropriateness Design and Markup Custom
[12]	Not available	(1) start the SUT (2) obtain the GUI's State (3) derive a set of sensible actions that a user could execute in a specific SUT's state (i.e. clicks, text inputs, mouse gestures) (4) select one of these actions (5) execute the selected action (6) apply the available oracles to check (in)validness of the new UI state. If a fault is found, stop the SUT (7) and save a re-playable sequence of the test that found the fault	Non-functional: Stability problems (crashes and exceptions) Linguistic: Mistranslation of a text on GUI (linguistic aspect)	With Lisa: Mistranslation With SAE: Syntactic Miscellaneous With MQM: Accuracy Custom
[13]	Over translation Placeholder Decoration	LocVer, short for Localization Verification, which is the original approach for systematic fixing of issues.	Linguistic	With Lisa: Mistranslation Style With SAE: Syntactic Miscellaneous With MQM: Accuracy Design and markup Custom

[14]	Not available	An online questionnaire-details and basis are not provided	Linguistic	With Lisa: With SAE: With MQM:
[15]	Functionalist and pragmatic inadequacies	Corpus-based approach to quality evaluation	Linguistic from pragmatic and Skops perspective	With Lisa: N/A With SAE: N/A With MQM: Audience appropriateness
[16]	Friendliness Casualness Professionalism Naturalness Easy-to-understand Appropriateness (grammatical errors , spelling) Correctness (untranslated words) Global satisfaction	An online questionnaire derived from definition of language quality in terms of items, including Friendliness Casualness Professionalism Naturalness Easy-to-understand Appropriateness (grammatical errors , spelling) Correctness (untranslated words) Global satisfaction	Linguistic	With Lisa: Mistranslation Language Country With SAE: Omission Syntactic Misspelling Miscellaneous With MQM: Terminology Accuracy Linguistic conventions Local conventions Custom
[17]	Lexical Syntactic Stylistic Typographic Pragmatic Localization Translation	Development of error topologies for website localization	Linguistic Cosmetic	With Lisa: Terminology Mistranslation style With SAE: Wrong term Syntactic Word structure Misspelling Punctuation Miscellaneous With MQM: Terminology Accuracy Style Local and linguistic conventions Custom
[18]	Typological and structural errors Lacked clarity Very technical Inconsistent terminology and usage Ambiguous terms Unfinished sentences Incorrect factual information Poor orthography Bad punctuation	An online questionnaire	Linguistic	With Lisa: Terminology Language Mistranslation With SAE: Wrong term Syntactic Punctuation Miscellaneous With MQM: Terminology Accuracy Linguistic conventions Custom
[19]	Consistency in terms of terminology	Comparative study	Linguistic	With Lisa: Terminology

With SAE:

Wrong term
Word structure
Misspelling

With MQM:

Terminology

Our Proposal	Terminology	MQM Core	Linguistic	With Lisa:
	Accuracy			Mistranslation
	Linguistic Conventions			Terminology
	Style			Language
	Locale conventions			Country
	Audience appropriateness			Consistency
				With SAE:
				Wrong Term
				Syntactic
				Omission
				Misspelling
				Punctuation
				Miscellaneous
				With MQM: The criteria are already selected from MQM core

In a study conducted by de Couto and Miranda [20], the scholars pointed out that there is a lack of research on automatic testing tools for supporting internationalization and localization. Their main aim was to reveal the state-of-the-art in internationalization and localization tested. Finally, they have proposed and evaluated automated solutions for supporting practitioners. In the first step, they have stated that they will accomplish systematic literature review to gain insight into the state-of-the-art in localization and internationalization testing. To this end, they have found 1073 papers and after applying their protocols, they have selected 24 primary studies. They expected to deduce a set of guidelines to be used by localization and internationalization testing community.

The research done by Ramler and Hoschek [10] has described a method used for automated testing of different localization variants of large software products. They claim that localization testing is used for checking the graphical user interface for missing translations, grammar and spelling issues, and layout problems. Their automation approach for localization testing is consisted of phases, namely, traversing the GUI, ripping GUI information and analyzing extracted data and generating test report. Similar to preceding studies, the study accomplished by Ramler and Hoschek [10] does not carry out the linguistic quality control based on established or prominent quality assessment model, like LISA, SAE J2450 or MQM.

Shang and Lin (2010)[21] focused on the critical success factors which are effective on the success of software localization. Based on the literature related to software localization and related management issues, they found propositions, and they believe that recent theses, reports and articles can be synthesized and classified into four categories, as below:

- a) infrastructure b) human capital C) management d) customer relations

They tested by collected data from a survey which is shared with professionals in the industry from 14 countries. For verification of the results, they conducted an interview.

The critical success factors are as below:

- ❖ Appropriate localization tools.
- ❖ Technical support.
- ❖ Appropriate communication facilities.
- ❖ Flexibility in dealing with changes
- ❖ Good project management systems.
- ❖ Reviewers are native speakers with technical project knowledge.
- ❖ The localization team is capable of writing in the language and terminology of the target audience
- ❖ Outsource workers have knowledge and technical skills.

- ❖ Localization team has good teamwork.
- ❖ Localization team is sensitive to language law and local customs.
- ❖ Localization team is familiar with localization tools and processes.
- ❖ Project managers provide translators with background information and answer questions.
- ❖ Determine the costs associated with the services provided.
- ❖ Well preserve project data and experiences for future use and reference.
- ❖ Maintain a diversified manpower pool for project needs.
- ❖ Establish measurements of qualitative and objectives during process.
- ❖ Have excellent marketing capability.
- ❖ Well manage project progress in accordance with customers' schedule.
- ❖ Build a trust relationship with customers.
- ❖ Well coordinate with multiple-level customers.
- ❖ Well manage the localization team in different fields to meet the requests from multiple-level customers.
- ❖ Define the services to ensure the customers' needs are satisfied.

In another study conducted by Boitet et al. [22], they have proposed two methods for better localization of the multilingual website: 1) an idea of that volunteer final users should be able to make a contribution to enhancement in the quality of the translated content 2) They have proposed interactive multilingual access gateway, which is dedicated to web site or domain, in order to solve the problem of higher quality multilingual access. In the context of language services and website localization, translation gateway is known as a translator between two systems which are based different communication protocols, data formats or languages, or even completely different architectures. Contrary to bridges simply communicating information, gateways repackage the received information to meet the needs of the destination system.

In another study, carried out by Awwad and Slany [11], an approach for automating the bidirectional localization testing for Android applications is proposed (Figure 2). They believe that automatic testing of localized software is important since the developers do not have sufficient knowledge about right-to-left language. The purpose of their methods is to detect any localization defects in the product. The proposed method is only for testing issues of bidirectional apps and it is specifically designed for Arabic language. The obtained results demonstrated the effectiveness of this method for revealing the deficiencies in the app's design.

Fig. 2. Localization testing architecture [11].

The proposed method for automatic testing, test the localized software considering following aspects: localized resources testing which is divided into fallback language and localized media and default resources, over translation, linguistic testing, cosmetic testing which is divided into view swiping direction and direction-sensitive graphics, auto layout in views, overlapping, elements positions, misalignment, text direction, string truncation validation, keyboard layout and functional testing.

In a thesis, conducted by Marin [23], the author has tried to make a comparison between five translation tools integrating assessment features considering two main aspects: assessment feature implementation and assessment data interoperability. To this end, 16 items were primarily inspired based on multidimension quality metrics. The obtained results indicate that computer-assisted translation environments do support the most basic characteristics of translation quality assessment (TQA), but there is much to do about the exchangeability of the assessment data. Although, in this study there an attempt to understand the integration of MQM model into the available TQL tools, but the corpora is mainly related to the domain of translation, not software localization. The tools which are examined are Fluency Now, MemoQ Translator Pro, SDL Trados Studio 2017, Translate5 and XTM Cloud. Among there none of them are for localization industry. It is worth noting that the MQM model is integrated into Fluency Now tools. Other tools which is designed to integrate the MQM framework from the beginning in collaboration with QTLaunchPad project. Moreover, SDL Trados Studio has LISA QA, MQM Core, SAE J2450 and TAUS_DFQ as the built-in models for quality assessment. Translate5 also comes with a built-in MQM metrics. XTM cloud provide the quality review resulted based on the harmonized MQM-DFQ error topology.

Martinez et al. [12] developed an academic prototype testing tool, called Test, which automatically and dynamically generates, executes and verifies test sequences based on a tree model, which derived from software user interface using assistive technologies. As a case study, they have employed this tool for checking the localization quality of a secure web platform, encompassing a set of applications as services. This platform was named eSigna, and their main concern was the localization quality of this product for Latin America community. To this end, using Test they were able to detect not only stability problems, like crashes and exceptions, but also they could analyze UI in terms of wrongly translated texts. During the implementation of the Test protocol, for localization correctness verification, the localization oracles must be settled. In fact, they prepared a list of taboo words that should not appear in the UI. For this purpose, the list was prepared using Java regular expressions. However, their testing tools for localization verification do not provide any report on error topologies, and there is no incorporation of any quality model or metric in Test tools.

Ørsted [13] has tried to devise a systematic validation for localization quality assurance across all languages. He claims there are reasons why the localization of a string can lead to bugs, both in user interface and function of the software product. These reasons are as below: Over-localization, buffer limitation, illegal characters, dependency, backward compatibility, uniqueness, placeholder and required string decoration. For instance, the localization of a placeholder is a common reason for a bug, since some localizable strings carry placeholders. If the placeholder is localized the program cannot drop the information into the placeholder and display it. For coping with these bug sources, in Microsoft, they use LocVer to create rules to describe the limitations for a given string, then run the rule engine against all languages (Figure 3)

Fig. 3. Graphical representation of LocVer (adopted from Ørsted 2008).

However, there are different need in each product, for this reasons, in one project, there may be need to excluded the specific rules and only include the generic rules, which is every applicable for certain placeholders. In a nutshell, in that study, the author focused on general rules used in Microsoft during localization quality assurance, and again we see that none of them are based on any de facto quality assurance metrics or models.

Omar [14] focused on localization quality of Learning Management Systems (LMSs) on the Arabic version of these systems, which is used by individuals and institutions all over the world. As a quality assessment instrument, they used online questionnaires to gain insight into the user experience. The results showed that translation inconsistencies are the main problems with Arabic version of the different LMs including Blackboard Learn, Microsoft Teams and Zoom. As a future study, they suggest to develop a quality matrix for encompassing all the dimensions and peculiarities of Arabic localization, MQM model, whose core structure assess the strings and target language text in terms of terminology, accuracy, linguistic conventions, audience appropriateness, design and markup and custom. The MQM 2.0 is defined based on following error types (adopted from <https://themqm.org/the-mqm-typology/>):

Terminology: Errors arise when a term does not conform to normative subject field or organizational terminology standards or when a term in the target content is not the correct, normative equivalent of the corresponding term in the source content. This category includes the errors categories, including inconsistent with terminology resource, inconsistent use of terminology and wrong term.

Accuracy: Errors occurring when the target content does not accurately correspond to the propositional content of the source text because of distortion, omission, or addition to the message. The sub-categories are mistranslation, over-translation, under-translation, addition, omission, do not translate and untranslated.

Linguistic conventions: Errors related to the linguistic well-formedness of the text, including problems with grammaticality, idiomaticity, and mechanical correctness. The sub-categories are: grammar, punctuation, spelling, Unintelligible, character encoding and textual conventions.

Style: Errors occurring in a text that are grammatically acceptable but are inappropriate because they deviate from organizational style guides or exhibit inappropriate language style. The sub-categories are organization style, third-party style, inconsistent with external reference, language register, awkward style, unidiomatic style and inconsistent style.

Local conventions: Errors occur when the translation product violates locale-specific content or formatting requirements for data elements. The sub-categories are number format, currency format, measurement format, time format, date format, address format, telephone format and shortcut key.

Audience appropriateness: Error where content Inappropriately uses a culture-specific reference that will not be understandable to the intended audience. The sub-categories are cultural-specific reference and offensive

Design and markup: Errors related to the physical design or presentation of a translation product, including character, paragraph, and UI element formatting and markup, integration of text with graphical elements, and overall page or window layout. The sub-categories are layout, markup tag, truncation/text expansion, missing text and link/cross reference

Custom: any other issue

Jiménez-Crespo [15] focused on the problem that current quality assurance models do not measure the pragmatic issues, and these models are componential error-based approaches and he points out that the relative lack of dialogue between the experts of localization industry and translation studies had led to the fact that the current localization evaluation are not based on theoretical models or solid empirical research. The author has attempted to set the foundation for an evaluation process that can serve for functionalist and pragmatic inadequacies using the localization evaluation corpora. In this foundation, the notions of corpus-evaluation and holistic translation assessment play a crucial role.

Bargas-Avila and Brühlmann [16] states that in today's world the software product has to run in multiple geographical and cultural regions, which necessitates the software developers to localize the user interface into many different languages. They have developed a language quality survey (LQS) which has a moderate correlation with an established usability metric, so called UMUX. As the study corpora, they use this LQS for quality assurance of three different products, namely, YouTube, Google Analytics and Good AdWords. The questionnaire items were derived from formal definitions of language quality, in terms of friendliness, casualness, professionalism, naturalness, easy-to-understand, appropriateness, correctness and global satisfaction.

Jiménez-Crespo [17] developed a corpus-based error topology, aiming to realize a more objective method for measuring quality in localization, particularly web localization, and to be more objective the methodology used is based on a monolingual comparable corpus of original and localized Spanish corporate websites. One of the error categories that their method has, which is absent in current testing instruments, is pragmatic error categories. They derived following error topologies for published localized websites (See Table 2).

Table 2. Error topologies for published localized websites (adopted from Jiménez-Crespo [17]).

Lexical	Syntactic	Stylistic	Typographic	Pragmatic	Localization	Translation
Loanwords	Syntactic calque	Phrasing/wording	Cacography	Appellative function	Untranslated segments	Opposite sense
Barbarisms	Formal/informal	Short sentence	Diacritical marks	Sociocultural norms	Segments in other languages	Wrong sense
Calques	Subject/verb agreement	Appellative function Register	Inconsistent capitalization	Explicitation	Encoding	Nonsense
False friends	Dialectal syntax	Ambiguity	Borrowings/capitalizations	Genre conventions	Incorrect syntax	Addition
Lexical coherence/superstructural	Prepositions	Omission/incomplete	Capitalized sentences	Cloned structure	Visual metaphor	Omission
Lexical coherence/microtextural	Gender or number		Capitalization/months, languages, etc.	Other pragmatic		
Wrong lexical item	agreement		Decades			
Acronyms	Pluralisation of acronyms		@ sign			
Punctuation or spaces in acronyms	Ambiguity		Punctuations/numbers			
Capitalization in acronyms			Format currencies			
Anglicisms in acronyms			Quotation marks			
			Capitalization/abbreviations			
			Ampersand (&)			

In a thesis conducted by Munyua [18], focused on localization quality of Google products. They tried to understand the impact of linguistic and cultural elements in terminology on the quality of the localized software in terms of their communicative effectiveness and overall achievements of the purpose. For quality assurance, Google uses a tool called Moravia, which is an extension added to Google Chrome. It checks errors, including inconsistent translation, number of value errors, terminology errors, incorrect placeholders and tags, punctuation errors and untranslated segments. For managerial purpose, Google uses Query Manager. It should be noted that, as it is obvious no specific or already established quality model is used during this study.

Gonçalves and Gonçalves [19] focused on comparing two tools (OpenOffice Writer and LibreOffice Writer) in their English version and theory associated translation or localization into Portuguese, in order to understand their level of terminological quality. For this purpose, using Computer Aided Translation tools they created bilingual tables to make a comparison between the source text and target text, and find out the terminology inconsistencies.

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design: Data Collection Methods and Case Studies: In the present study, two types of case studies will be the source of target and source texts as input for our tool that check the linguistic quality in an automatic way based on the error topologies defined by MQM. The first case study is a website which provides education consulting services for students interested in studying undergraduate and graduate programmes in Turkey, while the second type of the case study is financial software, for which we will study two financial software, namely, banking and accounting. It should be noted that the documentation of these two types of case studies will not be the source of input for the proposed tool. Indeed, the main source of the input will be based on graphical user interface of the both types of the case study.

Data Analysis Techniques: The objective of this research proposal is to explore the potential of machine learning for automating the quality assurance of localized software. To this end, machine learning algorithms, such as Decision Trees Random Forests, Support Vector Machines (SVM), Neural Networks (e.g., Convolutional Neural Networks, Recurrent Neural Networks) and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) can be adopted. These algorithms can be used to classify errors in the localized software, detect patterns and anomalies, and learn from user feedback to improve accuracy and effectiveness over time. It is worth noting that the main error topology for the afore-mentioned algorithms will be based on the topologies defined by MQM for linguistic errors. Moreover, the specific choice of algorithm will depend on the nature of the data and the goals of the study. This study proposes the use of machine learning techniques to automate the quality assurance process for localized software. The research will involve collecting data on localized software, including translations, screenshots, and user feedback. This data will be used to train machine learning models that can automatically identify and classify errors in the localized software. The study will evaluate different machine learning algorithms, such as decision trees, random forests, and neural networks, to identify the most effective approach. The quality assurance process will be evaluated by comparing the results of the machine learning model to those obtained through manual quality assurance processes. The study will also evaluate the effectiveness of the machine learning model in detecting and correcting errors in the localized software. Additionally, the study will explore the potential for the machine learning model to learn from user feedback to improve its accuracy and effectiveness over time.

6. EXPECTED OUTCOMES & IMPACT

The findings of this study can provide valuable implications for the potential of machine learning for automating the quality assurance of localized software. This can help organizations in the software localization industry to improve their efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance the quality of their localized software products. Additionally, the study can contribute to the advancement of machine learning methods for quality assurance in real-world contexts.

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